

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Narziyev Nosir Baxshilloyevich

SHORTEST JOB FIRST REJALASHTIRISH ALGORITMIDA

O'RTACHA KUTISH VAQTINI HISOBLASH

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/MAY

